
Better Economics for the Earth Joint Projects: A call for participation

Minh-Hoang Nguyen

AISDL Team

January 18, 2025

Since its official launch on June 22, 2022, the SM3D Portal has been committed to initiating and completing over a hundred Bayesian MindSponge Framework Collaborative Projects (BMF CP) [1,2]. Based on the principles of the successful BMF CP series, I, Minh-Hoang Nguyen, would like to propose a new type of collaboration in a parallel series: BEE JP.

BEE is an acronym for the book “Better Economics for the Earth,” while JP stands for Joint Paper [3].

The inspiration for the BEE JP series stems from the key idea of leveraging the power of humanities and social sciences in fostering an eco-surplus culture and promoting biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation [4-6]. Specifically, Joint Papers in this series aim to combine the humanistic values reflected through climate fiction [7-12] with the scientific theoretical systems, particularly the granular interactions thinking theory and the informational entropy-based notion of value [13], to establish logic and provide insights to achieve environmental sustainability.

Spring.

Additionally, the BEE JP series will facilitate in-depth exploration and critical thinking for environmental studies, including BMF papers. Experience shows that many elaborate empirical studies may fade into obscurity if they are not brought to light and explored further. The role of JP is to serve this purpose; however, it is not merely scientific communication, as it embodies genuine academic discourse and is often more authentic and innovative than empirical papers. For instance, a Joint Paper could be a discussion over a photograph of a Kingfisher taken nearly a century ago, which might have been forgotten, and its power to awaken human conscience for biodiversity conservation and nature protection [14]. Or it could be an opinion piece on how stories of kindness can contribute to building an environmental-healing culture within the beauty industry [15].

My proposal is also grounded in the success of previously implemented commentary projects. Opinion and commentary pieces of the AISDL team have enriched the literature on environmental research and guided future studies. They have been productively utilized

and well-cited globally since 2023 [16-23]. Therefore, I aim to replicate this success and share the methodology with the SM3D Portal community to contribute to a sustainable future collaboratively.

Projects within the BEE JP series will be numbered sequentially, starting from 1 since this call for participation. The outputs of this series will be diverse and not limited to specific approaches, including but not limited to essays, commentaries, perspectives, short opinions, and debate articles. Due to the shorter format of these contributions, each Joint Paper will have a maximum of 3-4 authors. The lead author of the joint paper will be responsible for presenting the key ideas and constructing the logic, facilitating the paper's presentation on the Portal for other members to register, coordinating, and eventually submitting the paper.

AISDL members may participate, depending on the scale of the paper. I will engage in discussions and serve as a mentor for Joint Papers in the series, but the mentor will NOT necessarily become an author.

I look forward to working with enthusiasts of future Joint Paper. Any portal user can visit Collaborative Project Topic to see if a new Joint Paper is open for registration and comment on it to express his/her interest in working with us. The person in charge will then confirm their participation in the project.

References

[1] Vuong QH. (2023). *Mindsponge Theory*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOC3WHZ2B3>

[2] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, La VP. (2022). *The mindsponge and BMF analytics for innovative thinking in social sciences and humanities*. Walter de Gruyter GmbH. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/8367405102/>

[3] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). *Better economics for the Earth: A lesson from quantum and information theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOD98L5K44>

[4] Nguyen MH. (2024). How can satirical fables offer us a vision for sustainability? <https://ojs.unito.it/index.php/visions/article/view/11267>

- [5] Nguyen MH. (2024). Five principles to leverage the humanistic values for biodiversity conservation and climate change mitigation. <https://mindsponge.info/posts/307>
- [6] Nguyen MH. (2024). A life-long humanistic journey to conservation practices. *Current Conservation*, **18**(3). <https://www.currentconservation.org/a-life-long-humanistic-journey-to-conservation-practices/>
- [7] Duong MPT. (2024). The art of satire and social commentary: From Animal Farm and Laugh or Lament to Wild Wise Weird. <https://zenodo.org/records/14169965>
- [8] Sari NPWP. (2024). Dear Kingfisher: A letter from a fan. <https://zenodo.org/records/14242470>
- [9] Tran TMA. (2024). Conversations with Kingfisher: Wisdom from Vuong's Wild Wise Weird Stories. <https://zenodo.org/records/14193362>
- [10] Ho MT. (2024). A minimal dose of self-reflective humor in Wild Wise Weird: The Kingfisher story collection. <https://philpapers.org/rec/HOROWC>
- [11] Li D. (2024). Wild Wise Weird: A timeless satire on humanity and nature. <https://philarchive.org/rec/WWWECK>
- [12] Huni C. (2024). Wild Wise Weird: A reflection of humanities. <https://zenodo.org/records/14242463>
- [13] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Further on informational quanta, interactions, and entropy under the granular view of value formation. <https://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4922461>
- [14] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). How an age-old photo of little chicks can awaken our conscience for biodiversity conservation and nature protection. *Visions for Sustainability*, **22**, 253-264. <https://doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/10982>
- [15] Nguyen MH, Nguyen QYT, Vuong QH. (2024). The beauty industry, climate change, and biodiversity loss. *Visions for Sustainability*, **22**, 235-251. <https://>

doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/10444

[16] Vuong QH, La VP, Nguyen MH. (2024). Weaponization of Climate and Environment Crises: Risks, Realities, and Consequences. *Environmental Science and Policy*, **162**, 103928. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2024.103928>

[17] La VP, Nguyen MH, Vuong QH. (2024). Climate change denial theories, skeptical arguments, and the role of science communication. *SN Social Science*, **4**, 175. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43545-024-00978-7>

[18] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH, Duong MPT, La VP. (2024). Radical climate activism: Motivations, consequences and approaches. *Visions for Sustainability*, **21**, 11-25. <http://dx.doi.org/10.13135/2384-8677/10237>

[19] Vuong QH, La VP, Nguyen MH. (2024). The overlooked contributors to climate and biodiversity crises: Military operations and wars. *Environmental Management*, **73**, 1089–1093. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00267-024-01976-4>

[20] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Call Vietnam mouse-deer ‘cheo cheo’ and let empathy save them from extinction: a conservation review and call for name change. *Pacific Conservation Biology*, **30**(3), PC23058. <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC23058>

[21] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024, Feb. 2). Forests of gold: carbon credits could be game-changing for Vietnam. <https://www.landclimate.org/forests-of-gold-carbon-credits-could-be-game-changing-for-vietnam/>

[22] Vuong QH, Ho MT. (2024). Escape climate apathy by harnessing the power of generative AI. *AI & Society*. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00146-023-01830-x>

[23] Vuong QH, Nguyen MH. (2024). Kingfisher: contemplating the connection between nature and humans through science, art, literature, and lived experiences. *Pacific Conservation Biology*, **30**(1), PC23044. <https://doi.org/10.1071/PC23044>

[24] Vuong QH. (2024). *Wild Wise Weird*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/BOBG2NNHY6>

©2025 AISDL - Science Portal for the [SM3D Knowledge Management Theory](#)